

Benefits of Using Music Therapy in Mental Disorders

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Abstract

This article presents a review of the use of music therapy in mental disorders studies searched from medical databases. The use of music as a form of therapy has shown beneficial effects in patients with psychological problems. In this analysis, the positive impact of music therapy in mental disorders is evidenced. They will present some of the results and findings of different studies which have shown the music therapy as a novel and emerging discipline. The results of the studies show that patients with mental disorders have therapeutic benefits in both psychosocial functioning and global functioning. Therefore, this therapy is proposed as an effective and enjoyable therapy for users.

Keywords: Music therapy; Mental disorders; Benefits; Practices

Introduction

Many studies have evidenced the beneficial effects of music therapy in patients with psychological disorders. In scientific literature, we have found empirically documented the emotional responses when people listen to music [1,2]. It has been demonstrated that patients with mental disorders perceive the expressiveness of the music the same way than without mental illness. The results support that the music is a good therapeutic modality for individuals with mental illness [3-5].

For the preparation of this section we have conducted a search in major medical databases (Medline, PubMed, Cochrane) and in some publications research in the form of doctoral theses (For lack of space are published in another number)¹. A search was conducted in the TESEO database about the topics which we discussed in this work, like schizophrenia disorder. About this issue, we found 144 records which, surprisingly, none is related to music therapy. We will use two of the most current doctoral theses which working with other therapeutic approaches-non music therapy- with people who suffering from schizophrenia disorder (2006)² (2007)³ [6,7] from Deusto University and Ramon Llull University. About doctoral theses on music therapy only 6 registers are located. Again, none of them had links with the collective interests us. We will name the last two theses to have a reference of what has been investigated in recent years [8-10] (2008)⁴ (2006)⁵ from Complutense University of Madrid, Spain. We have found several studies about the influence of music therapy on the symptoms of mental disorders. In this review we have collected the results obtained by researchers around the world in the study of music therapy in mental illness. In addition, we have focused in those studies whose findings have influenced a number of later investigations. Then we explained different studies about music therapy in mental disorders.

The Use of Music Therapy in Mental Health

The first revisited article evidence the influence of music therapy in the diversity of mental disorders. The seven subsequent studies are

focused on patients with schizophrenia. In the first study, [3] Loroño showed the benefit contribution that music therapy provided in the therapeutic process of patients with mental illness. It was an experience in the framework of a Mental Health Center during a year in Vizcaya. The center assists to patients from public assistance on an outpatient basis. The overall objective of this program was to provide the patient, a novel and aesthetic experience immersed in a therapeutic process which facilitated the development and personal, group and family growth. The family and social environment was closely linked to the therapeutic process, in which, person is an unique individual, from a physical, emotional, free and creative perspective. Other objectives of the sessions were to establish a space and time for relaxation in a context without words, establishing a communication code in rhythm, music listening, non-verbal, exploration, movement, improvisation, leaving a space to word at the end of the sessions. One of the most important aspects was to be able to explore intrapsychic ways of patients.

The findings of this study show that patients with severe mental illness have special difficulties in expression and communication and showed rejection in relationships. Therefore, in music therapy, patients will be able to be displayed themselves in a different context, favoring the expression of each one. The music therapist will be the facilitator and communication bridge. In this work, the relationship established with patients is essential and the most important. Music, instruments, games of creativity or expression are the working tools, working areas of the personality of difficult access with other therapeutic models. Music therapy allows new partnerships and resources. In addition, the author advises that we can use guidelines of active music therapy in the field of relational, experiential or where the communication is opened to the outside, or guidelines receptive music therapy addressed to the inside of each patient. It is important to work both ways because each patient has a different process.

The following investigation, Gold et al. [5] indicated that the goal of this therapy was to help people with severe mental illness to develop relationships and work different issues using the word exclusively. These

¹ For more information Montánchez "Music therapy in patients with chronic mental illness: Study group and individual case" (Master's thesis, non-Catholic University of Valencia, Spain).

² Called " Psychosocial rehabilitation in schizophrenia: predictors of success in the process of community integration".

³ Called "psychotherapeutic intervention in the initial phase of schizophrenia: Design and development of PIPE-Programme early intervention program in schizophrenia".

⁴ Called "The application of music therapy in the group of battered women. Two single case studies and an example of return".

⁵ Called "Influence of music therapy on the climate of coexistence in secondary schools".

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